

Thermodynamic Solution Stability Constants of Alkali Earth Metals with Hydroxamic Acids

R. D. ROSHANIA and Y. K. AGRAWAL

Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Technology and Engineering, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 001

Manuscript received 16 July 1982, revised 11 March 1983, accepted 24 June 1983

The thermodynamic metal-ligand stability constants of Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Ba^{2+} with hydroxamic acids in 60% dioxane-water media at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ have been determined. The effect of the ligand, central metal ion, ratio of the charge and radius, atomic number of the atoms and order of the stability constants is discussed. The stability constants of the alkali earth metal follows the order $\text{Be} > \text{Mg} > \text{Ca} > \text{Sr} > \text{Ba}$ with all the substituted hydroxamic acids.

HYDROXAMIC acids are versatile reagents in analytical chemistry¹⁻³, and are widely used in the analysis of trace metals^{4,5}. For a rational analytical application it is necessary to have the knowledge of the stability of the chelates formed. In the present investigation the pH-metric titration technique has been adopted for the determination of the metal-ligand stability constant of the alkali earths with hydroxamic acids.

Experimental

Hydroxamic acids : The hydroxamic acids were synthesised by the modified method of Agrawal *et al*⁶. They were recrystallized before use from benzene and petroleum ether mixture and dried over P_2O_5 .

Dioxane : Dioxane was purified by the method of Weissberger⁷.

Carbonate free water : The double distilled water was glass distilled and tested for the absence of carbonate and chloride⁸.

Potassium hydroxide (carbonate free) : This was prepared by the electrolytic method⁹ and the solution diluted to 0.1 M with the desired solvent composition. B.D.H., AnalaR potassium hydrogen phthalate was used for standardisation⁹. The solution always gave negative test for chloride and carbonate⁹.

Apparatus : N.P.L. certified graduated apparatus of Gallenkemp, Technico, grade 'A' was used for measurements. The 5 ml microburette was graduated to 0.01 ml.

pH meter : Systronic digital pH meter equipped with Systronic glass (0-14 pH) and saturated calomel electrodes was used for pH measurements.

Standard buffers : The pH meter was standardised at 35° with buffer solutions such as 0.05 M potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH 4.019 at 35°), 0.01 M borax (pH 9.100 at 35°)¹⁰ and National

Bureau of Standard buffers. Standardisation was checked before and after each titration by at least two buffers.

Metal salt solutions : Solutions were prepared from metal perchlorates in order to minimise the complexing of metal ions by anions. Since pure perchlorates of metals were not available, these were prepared by treating an excess of pure oxide or carbonate of metal with perchloric acid of requisite strength (to get neutral solutions). The solutions were filtered, boiled to remove any dissolved carbon dioxide and then suitably diluted. The concentrations of the perchlorates, Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Ba^{2+} , were determined volumetrically¹¹.

Titration procedure : A weighed quantity of hydroxamic acid (corresponding to 0.01 M in the final volume of 50 ml) was transferred into a dry, three-necked titration vessel, equipped with a pair of glass and calomel electrode, a limb for the burette tip and an inlet for nitrogen and 30 ml dioxane was added. Metal perchlorate (5 ml of 0.01 M), HClO_4 (5 ml of 0.05 M) and water (10 ml) were added. The mixture was thermostated at 35° and titrated against potassium hydroxide (0.1 M), prepared in 60% dioxane-water media, by adding small aliquots and recording the pH.

The thermodynamic stability constants were calculated as describes by Agrawal *et al*¹²⁻¹⁴.

Results and Discussion

The thermodynamic metal-ligand stability constants of the substituted N-p-chlorophenylbenzo-hydroxamic acid with $\text{Be}(\text{II})$, $\text{Mg}(\text{II})$, $\text{Ca}(\text{II})$, $\text{Sr}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Ba}(\text{II})$ in 60% dioxane-water media at 35° are given in Table 1.

The metal-ligand titrations show that the B values (pH meter readings) were sufficiently lower than the corresponding ligand (hydroxamic acid) titrations under the same conditions. The different metal-ligand concentrations gave almost identical results.

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF N-*p*-CHLOROPHENYL-BENZOHYDROXAMIC ACIDS IN 60% DIOXANE-WATER MEDIA AT 35°

Compound	Constants	Metal ions					
		H ⁺	Be ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺	Sr ²⁺	Ba ²⁺
N- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-benzohydroxamic acid	log K ₁	11.53	7.65	5.45	5.16	4.70	4.55
	log K ₂		6.40	4.30	4.10	4.00	3.80
	log K ₁ K ₂		14.05	9.75	9.26	8.70	8.38
	log K ₁ /K ₂		1.25	1.15	1.06	0.70	0.75
N- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -methoxybenzohydroxamic acid	log K ₁	11.80	8.70	6.43	6.15	5.75	5.53
	log K ₂		7.50	5.31	5.05	5.00	4.78
	log K ₁ K ₂		16.20	11.74	11.20	10.75	10.31
	log K ₁ /K ₂		1.20	1.12	1.10	0.75	0.75
N- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -chlorobenzohydroxamic acid	log K ₁	11.34	6.95	4.75	4.46	4.01	3.85
	log K ₂		5.75	3.65	3.41	3.29	3.11
	log K ₁ K ₂		12.70	8.40	7.87	7.30	6.96
	log K ₁ /K ₂		1.20	1.10	1.05	0.71	0.74
N- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl- <i>p</i> -bromobenzohydroxamic acid	log K ₁	11.30	6.90	4.69	4.42	3.96	3.81
	log K ₂		5.71	3.60	3.36	3.23	3.06
	log K ₁ K ₂		12.61	8.29	7.78	7.19	6.87
	log K ₁ /K ₂		1.19	1.09	1.06	0.73	0.75
N- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-cinnamohydroxamic acid	log K ₁	11.26	6.66	4.46	4.17	3.60	3.55
	log K ₂		5.46	3.32	3.12	2.86	2.80
	log K ₁ K ₂		12.12	7.78	7.29	6.46	6.35
	log K ₁ /K ₂		1.20	1.14	1.05	0.74	0.75
N- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-chloroaceto-hydroxamic acid	log K ₁	10.75	7.43	4.25	3.96	3.50	3.25
	log K ₂		6.20	3.15	2.91	2.76	2.50
	log K ₁ K ₂		13.63	7.40	6.87	6.26	5.75
	log K ₁ /K ₂		1.23	1.10	1.05	0.74	0.75

Since low concentration of metal ions were present, it indicates the possible absence of formation of polynuclear and protonated complexes. The maximum \bar{n} values obtained are almost 2 in all the cases and show only 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. No evidence was obtained for higher complexes. Since the variation in the stability constants at two temperature (25 and 35°) is very small, the constants were determined only at 35°.

The complex formation is believed to take place by the replacement of the hydroxylamine hydrogen by metal ion and ring closure through the carbonyl oxygen. The simple picture of the complex formation shows the similarity between hydroxamic acid and the first metal-ligand complex formed, MA⁺. In other words HA can be considered as the complex formed between the proton and the ligand ion A⁻. This analogy is further exemplified by the order in which the stabilities of the metal complexes and pK_a of the ligands vary. The pK_a values give a measure of the stabilities of the ligand proton complexes.

Ligand basicity and stability of the complex : Several workers have shown that an approximately linear relationship exists between the logarithm of the stability constants, log K₁ (or log K₂ or log β₂) of a series of closely related ligand^{1,2,19}. On this basis, it was expected that more basic ligands should give rise to more stable complexes. If the hydrogen ion is adopted as the standard ion, equations (1) and (2) can be formulated as¹⁹⁻²¹.

$$\log K_{MA} = B pK + \log K_{MA} - B pK_0 \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\log K_{MA} = c \log K_{MA_0} + pK - pK_0 \quad \dots (2)$$

Equation (1) holds good for the stability constants of the complexes of one metal with set of some substituted ligands. Equation (2) compares the stability constants of closely related ligands with a series of metal ions¹⁹⁻²¹. In the *p*-substituted N-*p*-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acids examined here, a linear relationship between pK_a and log K₁, log K₂ and log β₂ is observed for all the metal systems. The magnitude for the straight lines ($y = mx + C$ viz. $\log K_1 = mpK_a + \text{constant}$) calculated by the squares method are given by equations (3-7) for each metal ions.

$$\text{Be}^{2+} ; \log K_1 = 3.71 pK_a - 35.09 \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\text{Mg}^{2+} ; \log K_1 = 3.62 pK_a - 36.27 \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{Ca}^{2+} ; \log K_1 = 3.59 pK_a - 36.22 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{Sr}^{2+} ; \log K_1 = 3.79 pK_a - 39.09 \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\text{Ba}^{2+} ; \log K_1 = 3.58 pK_a - 36.72 \quad \dots (7)$$

It is evident from the pK_a values of the hydroxamic acids and logarithms of successive stability constants of the corresponding metal-ligand complexes (Table 1) that the introduction of *para* substituent has a parallel effect on the proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants viz.,

The same order is observed for log K₂ and log β₂ complexes of Be(II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Sr(II) and Ba(II) with *p*-substituted *p*-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamic acids and can be explained on the basis

of (i) ionic radii, (ii) electronegativity and (iii) ionization potential. It can be seen from the data given in Table I that $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ ($\log K_1, K_2$) have the order $\text{Be(II)} > \text{Mg(II)} > \text{Ca(II)} > \text{Sr(II)} > \text{Ba(II)}$. The same order of the stabilities of these metal chelates have been observed with amino barbituric acid - N,N-diacetic acid, β -alanine-N,N-diacetic acid and others²²⁻²⁵.

As the atomic number increases the stability constant decreases and may be due to the increase in the atomic radii of the metal ions. In all systems, the values of $\log K_1 > \log K_2$.

Ionic charge and atomic radius: It has been shown by Born that if ions are assumed to be spherical the energy of solution (e.g. solvation) of gaseous ions should be expressed by equation (8).

$$E = \frac{e^2}{r} \left(1 - \frac{1}{D} \right) \quad \dots (8)$$

where D is the dielectric constant, r = radius of ion, e = charge of the ion and E = energy charge.

In the present investigation a linear relationship is observed between the stability constants of Be(II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Sr(II) and Ba(II)-N-p-chlorophenylbenzohydroxamate complexes and e^2/r and $1/r$. In general it may be said that there is an increase in stability constant with increasing e^2/r or $1/r$ ¹⁸ viz., $\text{Be(II)} > \text{Mg(II)} > \text{Ca(II)} > \text{Sr(II)} > \text{Ba(II)}$.

Ionization potential :

Irving and Williams pointed out that the strength of coordinated bond between a metal ion and a ligand is governed by two factors. For metal ions of definite charge the ionic radius controls the contribution of purely electrostatic interaction between the metal and the ligand and the overall ionization potential of the metal for the process, $\text{M(gas)} \rightleftharpoons \text{M}^{2+}(\text{gas}) + \text{Ze}^-$, decides the affinity of central ion to accept electrons from the ligand in covalent bond formation²⁶. In the present study, since all the alkali earth metal ions are in +2 oxidation state, the electrostatic contribution to metal-ligand bond in the first complex formed with the same is assumed to be very nearly the same. Therefore, $\log K_1$ values for the metal complexes with different complexes were plotted against the respective overall ionization potential of Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Ba^{2+} ²⁷ to see the effect of the electron affinity of the alkali earth metals on the stability of the complexes they formed. In each case a straight line was obtained with one notable exception, the Mg^{2+} complexes show a negative deviation, e.g. the point corresponding to Mg(II) complexes falls lower on the straight line. This indicates that in each ligand system the stability of the first complex formed ($\log K_1$ or second complex $\log K_2$ or stability

constant $\log \beta_2$) was directly proportional to the total ionization potential of the central atom.

The ratio of successive stability constants :

As the tendency of the metal ion to take up ligand is proportional to the number of vacant sites, the ratio between consecutive constants, to a certain extent, is the stability determined²⁸. For anionic ligands, the coulombic attraction is more for M^{2+} as compared to MA^+ . As such $\log K_1 - \log K_2$ is usually positive²⁹. Table I shows that for all systems studies, $\log K_1 - \log K_2$ is positive and lies within 0.65-1.26 log units.

References

1. Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1980, **5**, 3.
2. Y. K. AGRAWAL and R. D. ROSHANIA, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1980, **89**, 159.
3. A. K. MAJUMDAR, "N-Benzoylphenylhydroxylamine and its Analogues", Pergamon, London, 1971.
4. Y. K. AGRAWAL and H. L. KAPOOR, *Analysis*, 1974, **5**, 62.
5. S. C. SHOME, *Analyst*, 1950, **75**, 27.
6. Y. K. AGRAWAL and S. G. TANDON, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1971, **16**, 371; 1971, **16**, 495; 1977, **22**, 70.
7. A. WEISSBERGER, E. S. PROSKAUER, J. A. RIDDICK and E. E. TOOPS, JR., "Techniques of Organic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1955, Vol. 7.
8. I. M. KOLTHOFF, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd Edn., Macmillan, London, 1961.
9. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis Including Elementary Instrumental Analysis", revised by J. BASSETT, R. C. DANNEY, C. M. JEFFERY and J. MCNDHAM, 4th Edn., Longman, 1978, p. 302.
10. R. A. ROBINSON and R. N. STOKES, "Electrolytic Solutions", Butterworths, London, 1961.
11. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid", Van Nostrand, New York, 1966.
12. Y. K. AGRAWAL and S. G. TANDON, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 1241.
13. Y. K. AGRAWAL and S. G. TANDON, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 869.
14. Y. K. AGRAWAL, D.Sc. Thesis, A. P. S. Univ., Rewa, 1979.
15. H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 72.
16. Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1977, **86**, 565.
17. Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1977, **108**, 713.
18. Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1979, **4**, 109.
19. Y. K. AGRAWAL, *Russ. Chem. Revs.*, 1973, **48**, 1773.
20. E. NREBOER and W. A. E. MCBRYDE, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1970, **48**, 2549.
21. E. NREBOER and W. A. E. MCBRYDE, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1970, **48**, 2565.
22. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKENS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1960, p. 18.
23. A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, "Chemistry of Metal Chelate Compounds", Prentice-Hall, Inc., New Jersey, 1952.
24. G. MATTOCK, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1954, **8**, 777.
25. G. H. NAOCOLLAS, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **24**, 108.
26. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 5192.
27. F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", 2nd Edn., Wiley Eastern Ltd., 1977.
28. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solutions", P. Hasse, Copenhagen, 1941.
29. "Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes", Part I, The Chemical Soc., London, Special Publication, 1957.